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PRESS RELEASE

Joint Communication StandICT.eu & HumanTech

PRESS RELEASE: Standards Supporting Smarter and Greener Construction in Europe

Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) signed between HumanTech & StandICT.eu

PISA – Italy, 17 04 2023 –StandICT.eu & HUMANTECH announce their collaboration to foster standardisation as an integral part of the European research and innovation landscape.

Since 2018, [StandICT.eu](https://standict.eu) is building on its success in fostering the European participation in international ICT standardization. The project has several key axes - firstly, it will fund **400+ European standardisation experts** in a series of 9 Open calls, providing 3M€ of funding. Secondly, it manages the [European Observatory for ICT Standardisation \(EUOS\)](#), an interactive online ecosystem including an up-to-date standards repository and a nest for technical working groups sharing insights about **ongoing standardisation efforts across different initiatives**. Furthermore, with its [ICT Standards Academy](#), StandICT contributes to **training next-generation ICT standardisation experts**.

[HumanTech](#) is working towards Human-centred technologies for a safer and greener construction industry through the use of AI, Robotics and Wearables. Sharing Proposals for Open Standards, such as novel BIM extended Digital Twin (BIMxD) ontologies (entities, models and representations) with the wider scientific and construction engineering community through appropriate standardisation bodies, involved in the maintenance and expansion of the IFC framework, is one of the objectives of the project.

StandICT.eu focuses on horizontal and vertical ICT fields as defined in the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation¹, including **industry 4.0, AI and robotics** that are at the core of HumanTech as well. Both projects support standardization as a tool for making the European construction sector greener and smarter. We believe that this MoU can consolidate even further these commitments on both sides.

“With this collaboration, StandICT.eu community grows towards the smart construction sector, which is one of the key areas of the European sustainable growth. I am looking forward to have the HumanTech researchers contributing to the StandICT.eu Open Calls and the related technical working groups. I also believe that the standardization experts of our StandICT.eu community could support HumanTech’s path

¹https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/european-standards/ict-standardisation_en

*in future standardization. ”, aligns **Mona Marill**, StandICT Fellowship Programme Manager, from AUSTRALO Marketing Lab.*

*“One key activity of HumanTech is identifying significant opportunities to push contributions into future standards, pre-normative activities and open collaborative development environments. This collaboration with StandICT.eu is an important milestone and an excellent chance to enable HumanTech standardisation partners to participate in the identified and prioritised standardization activities, as well as contribute to reinforcing our commitment to the Standardisation ecosystem” says **Giulia Pastor**, HumanTech WP8 – Outreach, Collaboration and Exploitation leader, from AUSTRALO Marketing Lab.*

As both projects are invested supporting the creation of new ICT standards, this collaboration will help our experts to create synergies and share resources. Furthermore, the StandICT.eu Open Calls can be beneficial for HumanTech stakeholders. Vice-versa, the HumanTech experts will bring value notably to the EUOS by sharing their success stories and insights from the concerned ICT areas. Foremost, our aim is that thanks to this collaboration, the European experts can boost their standardisation work on both sides.

StandICT.eu 2026

For more information on StandICT.eu 2026, contact us at info@standict.eu and follow us on our social media channels: [Twitter](#) | [Linkedin](#) | [YouTube](#)

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Consortium: [Dublin City University](#) (IE) - Financial and Administrative Coordinator, [Trust-IT Srl](#) (IT) - Technical Coordinator, [OpenForum Europe](#) (BE), [AUSTRALO](#) (ES), [European Digital SME Alliance](#) (BE), and [Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research ISI](#) (DE).

HumanTech

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Grant Agreement N° 101058236.

Consortium: <https://humantech-horizon.eu/team/>